

Blood glucose

Treatment animal	Day-1 (Before treatment)	Day-2	Day-3	Day-4	Day-5	Day-6	Day-7
Control-1	88		87	99	82	101	86
Control-2	98		85	90	94	88	83
Control-3	89		85	90	87	80	86
Control-4	105		99	110	93	82	87
Control-5	99		103	98	84	80	101
Control-6	94		90	105	87	83	88
Control-7	110		89	93	102	87	85
Control-8	97		110	102	88	92	90
Control-9	88		85	90	82	93	105
Control-10	90		95	87	80	103	88

Treatment animal	Day-1 (Before treatment)	Day-2	Day-3	Day-4	Day-5	Day-6	Day-7
Alloxan 110 mg- 1	88		100	92	80	85	91
Alloxan 110 mg- 2	93		302	254	199	135	116
Alloxan 110 mg- 3	82		87	92	80	89	84
Alloxan 110 mg- 4	96		287	201	130	101	95
Alloxan 110 mg- 5	102		268	300	296	302	280
Alloxan 110 mg- 6	94		87	93	103	100	85
Alloxan 110 mg- 7	83		89	80	92	87	82

Alloxan 110 mg- 8	80		105	87	89	93	81
Alloxan 110 mg- 9	97		88	109	100	84	93
Alloxan 110 mg- 10	90		106	98	87	83	86

Treatment animal	Day-1 (Before treatment)	Day-2	Day-3	Day-4	Day-5	Day-6	Day-7
Alloxan 120 mg- 1	87		89	105	88	94	97
Alloxan 120 mg- 2	92		345	332	256	294	289
Alloxan 120 mg- 3	86		320	299	287	266	275
Alloxan 120 mg- 4	89		305	Death	-	-	-
Alloxan 120 mg- 5	78		90	84	87	90	81
Alloxan 120 mg- 6	85		233	287	305	284	265
Alloxan 120 mg- 7	85		268	240	153	119	98
Alloxan 120 mg- 8	91		352	Death	-	-	-
Alloxan 120 mg- 9	84		287	254	184	141	119
Alloxan 120 mg- 10	93		294	288	245	274	282

Treatment animal	Day-1	Day-2	Day-3	Day-4	Day-5	Day-6	Day-7
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	(Before treatment)						
Alloxan 130 mg- 1	82		253	278	221	135	120
Alloxan 130 mg- 2	87		Death	--	-	-	-
Alloxan 130 mg- 3	95		354	241	228	186	145
Alloxan 130 mg- 4	99		378	Death	-	-	-
Alloxan 130 mg- 5	83		324	294	286	289	302
Alloxan 130 mg- 6	86		366	333	323	302	312
Alloxan 130 mg- 7	102		98	87	85	90	105
Alloxan 130 mg- 8	94		302	355	345	308	394
Alloxan 130 mg- 9	81		356	287	268	195	133
Alloxan 130 mg- 10	88		344	356	311	321	298

Treatment animal	Day-1 (Before treatment)	Day-2	Day-3	Day-4	Day-5	Day-6	Day-7
Alloxan 140 mg- 1	98		355	342	304	331	312
Alloxan 140 mg- 2	87		Death	-	-	-	-
Alloxan 140 mg- 3	88		257	241	220	153	119

Alloxan 140 mg- 4	102		322	Death	-	-	-
Alloxan 140 mg- 5	81		288	295	287	278	265
Alloxan 140 mg- 6	86		Death	-	-	-	-
Alloxan 140 mg- 7	93		122	102	88	82	93
Alloxan 140 mg- 8	100		314	325	287	268	287
Alloxan 140 mg- 9	97		358	322	312	290	293
Alloxan 140 mg- 10	84		302	319	310	286	267

Treatment animal	Day-1 (Before treatment)	Day-2	Day-3	Day-4	Day-5	Day-6	Day-7
Alloxan 150 mg- 1	87		355	382	337	302	394
Alloxan 150 mg- 2	80	Death	-	-	-	-	-
Alloxan 150 mg- 3	83		345	Death	-	-	-
Alloxan 150 mg- 4	102		395	382	398	387	373
Alloxan 150 mg- 5	109		285	298	277	290	287
Alloxan 150 mg- 6	98		Death	-	-	-	-
Alloxan 150 mg- 7	102		354	288	292	279	277

Alloxan 150 mg- 8	83		315	278	270	276	281
Alloxan 150 mg- 9	86		296	311	295	302	298
Alloxan 150 mg- 10	90		Death	-	-	-	-

Treatment animal	Day-1 (Before treatment)	Day-2	Day-3	Day-4	Day-5	Day-6	Day-7
Alloxan 160 mg- 1	84		302	298	285	278	257
Alloxan 160 mg- 2	99	Death	-	-	-	-	-
Alloxan 160 mg- 3	102		Death		-	-	-
Alloxan 160 mg- 4	91		306	389	354	339	288
Alloxan 160 mg- 5	82		339	Death	-	-	-
Alloxan 160 mg- 6	97	Death	-	-	-	-	-
Alloxan 160 mg- 7	103		320	300	287	309	293
Alloxan 160 mg- 8	110	Death	-	-	-	-	-
Alloxan 160 mg- 9	80	Death	-	-	-	-	-
Alloxan 160 mg- 10	78		257	268	274	298	282

Treatment animal	Day-1	Day-2	Day-3	Day-4	Day-5	Day-6	Day-7
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	(Before treatment)						
Alloxan 170 mg- 1	88	Death	-	-	-	-	-
Alloxan 170 mg- 2	81		Death	-	-	-	-
Alloxan 170 mg- 3	93	Death	-	-	-	-	-
Alloxan 170 mg- 4	102	Death	-	-	-	-	-
Alloxan 170 mg- 5	95		388	Death	-	-	-
Alloxan 170 mg- 6	84		369	Death	-	-	-
Alloxan 170 mg- 7	83	Death	-	-	-	-	-
Alloxan 170 mg- 8	77		354	301	371	324	313
Alloxan 170 mg- 9	109	Death	-	-	-	-	-
Alloxan 170 mg- 10	88		392	352	357	302	297

Table:

Animal Group	TC	TA1	TA2	TA3	TA4	TA5	TA6	TA7
Mortality %	0	0	20	20	30	40	60	80
Diabetic %	0	10	40	40	50	60	40	20
Nonresponsive %	0	70	20	10	10	0	0	0
Auto reversal %	0	20	20	30	10	0	0	0

Effects of Alloxan

